

ХАРАКТЕРНЫЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ ТЕЧЕНИЯ ТЯЖЕЛЫХ ПНЕВМОНИЙ У ДЕТЕЙ РАННЕГО ВОЗРАСТА НА ФОНЕ С ВРОЖДЕННЫМИ АНОМАЛИЯМИ РАСЩЕЛИНЫ ВЕРХНЕЙ ГУБЫ И НЁБА

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Abstract. *In this study, clinical and anamnestic features of the course of severe pneumonia in early age children with congenital anomalies of the cleft lip and palate were observed with analysing of life history and current condition of the children. Research methods are analysis, clinical observations, X-ray studies. Clinical and anamnestic features of the course of severe pneumonia in early age children with congenital anomalies of the cleft lip and palate were determined. It was revealed that the severity of the condition of examined children was due to a burdened maternal history, premorbid background, artificial feeding and prematurity factor itself and such conditions of the microflora of the gastrointestinal tract.*

Keywords: *pneumonia, congenital anomalies of cleft lip and palate, young children, clinic, X-ray studies.*

Аннотация. Был обследован 45 детей с внебольничной пневмонией на фоне с врожденными аномалиями расщелины верхней губы и неба и определено клинко-анемнестические данные с помощью анализа история жизни и течение данного заболевания ребенка. Выявлены, что тяжесть состояния обследованных детей была обусловлена отягощенным материнским анамнезом, преморбидным фоном, искусственным вскармливанием и самим фактором недоношенности, а такие состояний микрофлоры желудочно-кишечного тракта.

Ключевые слова: *пневмония, врожденные аномалии расщелины верхней губы и неба, дети раннего возраста, клиника, рентгенологические исследования.*

Аннотация. Ушбу тадқиқотида 45 нафар эрта ёшдаги бемор болаларда юқори лаб ва танглай кемтиклиги асосидаги ўткир зотилжамнинг клиник-анамнестик кечиши, касаллик тарихини ва болаларнинг хозирги холатини тахлил қилиш орқали ўрганилади. Туғма юқори лаб ва танглай кемтиклиги бор эрта ёшдаги болаларда зотилжамнинг кечишини, шунингдек ошқозон-ичак тизими микрофлорасидаги ўзгаришларга боғлиқлиги аниқланади. Тадқиқот усуллари: анамнез, клиник кузатув, рентгенологик теширувлар.

Калит сўзлар: *зотилжам, туғма юқори лаб ва танглай кемтиклиги, клиника, рентгенологик теширувлар.*

Relevance.

Acute pneumonia in young children remains a significant cause of morbidity and mortality, despite the introduction of potent broad-spectrum antimicrobial agents, the availability of comprehensive supportive treatment regimens, and preventive measures (2; 4; 5). A poor background for the course of pneumonia includes rickets, protein-energy malnutrition, anemia, dysbiosis, atopic dermatitis, and others (3).

Patients with congenital anomalies of the tissues and organs in the maxillofacial area hold a special place in the study of pneumonia. Of particular interest is the evaluation of the clinical course of acute pneumonia in these premature infants. However, despite this interest, the literature lacks sufficient theoretical or applied studies on the treatment of this group of patients. Treatment is associated with special difficulties, requiring the participation of highly qualified specialists and a consistent, comprehensive approach.

For a long time, certain external factors have been considered to play a role in the origin of congenital anomalies such as cleft lip and palate (CLP), including diseases of the mother during pregnancy (infectious diseases, uterine diseases, artificial or spontaneous miscarriages), psychological trauma, poor nutrition, and others (1). CLP represents a severe developmental defect, leading to significant consequences. From the moment of birth, the child exhibits pronounced dysfunction of the lips and palate, affecting the ability to suckle, swallow, and later chew, which leads to developmental deviations and sometimes death in the early weeks of life. In children with CLP, the processes of feeding, swallowing, and breathing are severely impaired. This can lead to aspiration of oral cavity contents and various respiratory complications, including lung issues (1; 3).

The aforementioned data emphasize the need to study the clinical and anamnestic features of acute pneumonia in children with congenital anomalies of the upper lip and palate.

Objective of the Study: To analyze the clinical and anamnestic features of acute pneumonia in young children with congenital cleft lip and palate anomalies.

Materials and Methods: We analyzed 45 medical records of children with severe acute pneumonia and congenital cleft lip and palate (CLP), and 18 preterm infants with a birth weight ranging from 1500g to 1800g and an age of 3 to 11 days.

Results and Discussion: The mothers' ages ranged from 19 to 49 years: 5% of them were under 20 years old, 23% were between 20-25 years old, and 51% were experiencing their first pregnancy. In 3% of cases, the outcomes of previous pregnancies were unfavorable (miscarriage, stillbirth, premature delivery). Fetal protein-energy deficiency was observed in 17%. Gynecological diseases were noted in 11% of the mothers.

Chronic infections and diseases such as pyelonephritis, glomerulonephritis, rheumatism, diabetes mellitus, obesity, and acute and chronic bronchitis were present in 24.6% of the women. Acute respiratory viral infections (ARVI) with high fever were experienced by 16.2% of the women during the first half of pregnancy, and by 6% in the second half. Pregnancy was often accompanied by complications: early toxicosis in 32.6% of cases; preeclampsia of varying severity in 27%; the threat of pregnancy termination in 18%; and chronic intrauterine hypoxia in 8%. Infectious diseases occurred in 20% of cases. Deliveries were on time in 67.15% of cases, while premature or late deliveries accounted for 33.0%. Among complications, premature rupture of membranes occurred in 12%, and the anhydrous interval lasting from 6 to 12 hours occurred in 11%. Abnormal labor was observed in 4% of women, and labor stimulation was required in 2% of the mothers.

At birth, 7% of newborns had Apgar scores of 7-8 points, 25% had scores of 4-5 points, and 5% had scores of 3-4 points.

The clinical course study showed that the temperature remained normal throughout the illness in most children (12), while the disease progressed against a high fever of 39%. All examined preterm infants with CLP had pneumonia, which manifested with respiratory distress syndrome and cyanosis (2) either upon admission or within 2-3 days. Intestinal syndrome developed either from the beginning of the disease or 2-3 days after admission and remained

predominant throughout the acute period. The diagnosis of pneumonia was confirmed radiologically: focal shadows were detected in 14 children, and confluent shadows in three children upon lung radiography.

Conclusion.

The data obtained indicate that the severity of the condition in the examined children was due to a complicated maternal history, predisposing background conditions, artificial feeding, and the fact of prematurity itself. A child with low birth weight and various forms of immunodeficiency has intestinal flora that becomes pathogenic, provoking inflammatory processes both in the intestines and lungs. The effectiveness of therapy depends on the individual choice of treatment, taking into account the etiology of the disease, its course, and the phase of the pathological process, the patient's age, and the degree of extrapulmonary lesions in the body.

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